

Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction Part III Interference

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In Parts I and II we considered the problem of a beam of light A moving in the positive x direction striking a medium at $x=0$ and reflecting B and refracting C. This is a probabilistic problem because a single photon has a probability to reflect and another to refract. We also noted that conservation of energy holds i.e. $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$ where $I(A), I(B)$ and $I(C) > 0$ are intensities. The goal is to find $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ given $I(A)$, but there is only one equation and two unknowns.

In Part I we argued that an energy conservation equation incorporates two equations representing square root type probabilities. In Part II we argued that a physical motivation for such a situation may be that in a steady state case, one has dynamic directional probabilities not just static ones. The static/classical probability is associated with the conservation of energy and groups by time i.e. an incident beam exists during one time range and reflected and refracted beams during another. One, however, may create a steady state system so that all three beams exist at the same time, although the reflected and refracted beams at any instant are the result of incident photons which hit the medium at an earlier time. A steady state system should not rely on time, but still contains probabilities. There is thus no reason to group by time, but rather one groups by space with the incident and reflected beams in one region and the refracted in another.

Introducing space grouped dynamic probabilities A,B,C one may write (using conservation of probability and average momentum): $A+B = C$ ((1a)) and $p_1A - p_1B = p_2C$ ((1b)) where $p_1 = n_1p$ and $p_2 = n_2p$ and $c_1 = c/n_1$ and $c_2 = c/n_2$. The second equation has the appearance of a conservation of energy equation if one places the term $-p_1B$ on the RHS. The problem is that $A+B=C$ implies B must be negative if $n_1 < n_2$. Thus dynamic probabilities may be negative (which is unusual) and the second equation cannot be conservation of energy although it is of the correct form. In Part II we noted one may multiply the two equations together and by using a difference of squares preserve the form of an energy conservation equation which now has AA, BB and CC terms which are necessarily positive and may be identified with $I(A), I(B)$ and $I(C)$.

In this note we wish to consider the consequences of B being negative. This we suggest implies A and B interfere so that $A+B$ yields a number smaller than A i.e. C for $n_1 < n_2$. As a result the negative value of B allows for conservation of probability (or photons). At first this may seem a mathematical convenience, but the two equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) lead to physical consequences, namely the probabilities BB and CC in terms of AA. We thus speculate that there might be a physical mechanism associated with the minus value of B, the reflected ray. This physical property (which should exist for individual photons) ensures conservation of probability.

If one considers a glass wedge (or thin film) in air one has reflection from the glass ($n_1 < n_2$) bringing in a minus sign in B (for conservation with the incident beam). The refracted beam becomes the new incident beam within the glass and reflects at an $n_1 > n_2$ interface so B' is not negative. B and B' may now interfere (depending on the thickness of the wedge) creating an interference pattern which must conserve probability overall. In general one would expect B and

B' to be independent, but each carries conservation of probability information (in a physical form) and this information is different causing interference to occur.

Reflection and Refraction from a Medium

Consider a light beam moving in the positive x direction hitting a medium at $x=0$ such that part of the beam reflects and the rest refracts. Considering a single photon, it has a certain probability to reflect and another to refract such that the sum is 1. If one thinks in terms of single photons which retain their energy and remain intact, then energy conservation is automatically guaranteed and so it seems almost a little strange to write a conservation of energy equation (1):

$$I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2 \quad ((2))$$

Here $I(A)$, $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ are the intensities of the incident, reflected and refracted beams and are necessarily positive. What the energy conservation equation shows is that one has two unknowns (if $I(A)$ is known) and only one equation. In part I we suggested writing:

$$I(A)/c_1 - I(B)/c_2 = I(C)/c_2 \quad ((3))$$

((2)) is grouped according to time i.e. the incident beam exists during one time interval and then is converted into reflected and refracted beams which exist during another. ((3)), however, is grouped in space suggesting time does not exist. This may be physically arranged if one has a steady state situation. In such a case one may make use of the property of "difference of squares" to preserve the form of ((3)), but obtain two equations allowing for one to solve for $I(B)$ and $I(A)$ namely:

$$A + B = C \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 A - p_1 B = C \quad ((4b))$$

One may note these equations are grouped spatially and that B is negative if $n_1 < n_2$. Multiplying the two together, however, creates a difference of squares form. Thus associating $I(A)$ with AA etc leads to conservation of energy, yet ((4a)) and ((4b)) may be used to solve for B, C in terms of A and obtain the physically observable BB and CC values.

Interference

For the case of $n_1 < n_2$, B and C magnitudes must be less than the magnitude of A . Taking A to be given and positive implies B must be negative for C to have a smaller magnitude than A . Equations ((4a) and ((4b)), however, are in the form of probability conservation grouped by space. In other words A and B are grouped together because the incident and reflected beams exist in the same region of space, while the refracted exists in another. All beams exist at the same time in a steady state scenario. A negative B value indicates that the incident and reflected intensities somehow partially cancel (interfere) to account for the diminished refracted intensity existing in $x > 0$. Thus one considers conservation of probability.

At first this seems like mathematical artifice needed to create a conservation scenario (i.e. ultimately conservation of energy). Conservation of energy, however, already exists without any equation regarding intensities because each incident photon remains intact and retains its energy whether it reflects or refracts. Thus ((4a)) and ((4b)) should have physical relevance as they yield B and C which lead to the physical observables BB and CC.

This seems to be an unusual situation. A beam of incident light and in fact a single incident photon upon reflecting in a $n_1 < n_2$ scenario manifests a physical property equivalent to the minus sign of B. This physical property ensures conservation of probability in a steady state situation, but should also exist even if there is no steady state (as it is a physical property). This leads to an interesting consideration.

A Glass Wedge in Air (Or Thin Film Interference)

In the above section we suggested a reflecting photon with $n_1 < n_2$ “picks up” a physical property akin to a minus sign such that it may “interfere” with an incident beam to reduce probability. This physical property should thus exist even for a single photon whether or not there is a steady state situation. Consider a glass wedge in air with a surface along the x axis. Incident photons (moving in the -y direction) hit the surface ($n_1 < n_2$), reflect and receive the physical property linked to -B. The refracted beam then moves in the glass and becomes the new incident beam A' striking the glass-air interface $n_1 > n_2$. There is reflection, but no minus sign and no special property for these photons. Thus B and B' carry different properties associated with their own particular conservation of probability scenarios.

Both sets of photons now move in the positive y direction and interfere at a screen because they have different properties i.e. B is minus and B' is not. Overall probability must be conserved, but B being minus may remove probability from one space region and add it to another (for conservation to hold). This suggests a periodic type of pattern associated with light (i.e. a set of wavelengths) and gives rise to the experimentally observed interference pattern. One may note that if a wavelength or characteristic length exists then a minus sign is equivalent to a phase shift of 180 degrees and twice the width of the wedge also affects B'. Thus this also must be taken into account.

We thus argue that such considerations lead to the notion of light (even a single photon) being associated with a spatial wavelike pattern which may interfere to conserve probability i.e. probability is removed from one spatial region and placed in another.

Physical Manifestation

In the above section an unusual suggestion was made that a photon is associated with a probability wave which is used to ensure conservation of probability. Thus there seems to be a specific reason for wavelike behaviour. For example, a photon moving in air and hitting glass ($n_1 < n_2$) picks up a 180 degree phase shift so it may negatively interfere with an incident beam in a steady state picture to account for the reduced intensity of the refracted beam relative to the incident. This conservation of probability is based on a spatial grouping with no existence of time.

We argue that this is a physical property which holds for a single photon even if there is not a steady state. This begs the question: What is this property? For a photon it is the oscillating magnetic and electric fields. These fields naturally interfere with others and energy density is given by $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 B^2$. This still does not answer the question: Why are there magnetic and electric fields if there is no charge or current and what causes the oscillations?

For a particle with mass one cannot use the electric/magnetic field argument, but may argue that even for uniform motion, the particle creates a probability wave. This still does not answer the question of the exact nature of this probability wave.

A main point we wish to stress is that in both cases wave properties lead to interference which may be used to ensure some type of conservation. (We have argued in previous notes that for reflection or refraction with the incident beam making an angle with the y axis and the medium/mirror along the x, the wave nature ensures conservation of momentum in the x direction.)

Conclusion

In this note we have considered a beam of light moving in the positive x direction which reflects and refracts at $x=0$. Incident $I(A)$, reflected $I(B)$ and refracted $I(C)$ intensities (all >0) exist and one must find $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ in terms of $I(A)$. This requires two equations. A conservation of energy equation holds (1): $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$. This groups by time. What is the second equation?

We argued in Parts I and II that one may consider two square root type equations $A+B=C$ and $p_1A - p_1B = p_2C$ which when multiplied together yield conservation of energy with $AA=I(A)$ etc. In such a case, A, B and C have the appearance of probabilities (called dynamic probabilities in Part II), but B is negative for $n_1 < n_2$ so the magnitude of C is smaller than that of A.

In this note we argue that a reflected photon receives a special property equivalent to B being negative if it reflects in a $n_1 < n_2$ situation. This property allows for the partial cancellation or interference with newer incident photons in a steady problem so that probability is conserved. Even though energy is conserved there is an interference between the incident and reflected beams because they exist in the same region of space and this region cannot have overall more probability than the region $x > 0$ only containing the reflected beam. At first this seems like a mathematical artifice, but we present the well-known example of a wedge in air (thin film) to manifest this experimentally. Two different reflected rays, each with their own different conservation of probability property, interfere (if one also considers the width of the wedge or film). This leads to light being absent in some x places and augmented in others so that overall probability is conserved. Ultimately, however, the minus sign of a reflected ray ($n_1 < n_2$), manifested physically, is associated with conservation of probability. Thus we suggest that wave behaviour of both light and particles is a physical mechanism associated with conservation laws in nature.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change